

Low-Cost Methodology for Estimation of Breast Shape using Microwave Signals

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Abstract

The retrieval of the body shape can be crucial ahead of medical Microwave Imaging (MWI) reconstruction. Current state-of-the-art methods provide accurate estimations of the body shape but they require additional hardware and may be computationally intensive and time-consuming. In this paper, we propose a simple method using the original measurements of an MWI acquisition, and we assess the performance of the method under different conditions. The results show the estimation accuracy varies with the complexity of the shape under examination, antenna configuration and data source. The estimated median errors for some antenna positions were as low as 0.4 mm. An optimised estimation was obtained by fine-tuning parameters for each simulated or experimental scenario.

1 Introduction

Medical Microwave Imaging (MMWI) has been studied as an alternative and/or complementary imaging modality for some medical diseases or conditions, such as breast cancer diagnosis [1], brain stroke detection [2], and bone osteoporosis [3]. MMWI uses low power, is low cost, is non-invasive, and is comfortable for the patient, making it an attractive imaging alternative for diagnosis or monitoring.

For most MMWI applications, knowledge about the shape of the body under examination and antenna positioning is essential to ensure an accurate image reconstruction. In Microwave Tomography (MWT), an *initial guess* model is needed to run and solve the inverse scattering problem [4]. For radar imaging, the body shape is needed to calculate the traveled distances in each medium, which are needed for commonly-used image reconstruction algorithms. In many radar-based MMWI prototypes, the antennas are touching the body and thus the retrieval of the body shape is not needed as the body conforms to a known antenna distribution. However, there are radar-based prototypes that do not require antennas to touch the body. This is the case of some antenna configurations for breast [5] or axillary [6] microwave imaging prototypes.

Some methodologies have been proposed to estimate body shape, but they require additional scanning time [7] or hard-

ware. This hardware include optical devices such as infrared stereoscopic cameras [5], webcams [8], laser systems based on a single laser [9] or multiple laser scanners [10], or hybrid methods with cameras and lasers [11].

In this paper, we present a low-cost and computationally efficient methodology for body shape estimation using radar-based MMWI prototypes, and evaluate its performance in simulation and experimental settings. Although not as accurate as previously presented more complex methods, this methodology does not require additional hardware and can be a suitable option for early stages of development of low-cost devices.

2 Methodology

2.1 Shape estimation

The proposed shape estimation methodology uses the backscattered monostatic signals recorded by each antenna. After removing the antenna response (with a free-space measurement), the first reflection recorded in the signals should correspond to the skin or surface reflection and can be used to define reference points of the body shape.

The intensity of the backscattered signals can be written as a function of distance considering the wave-migration algorithm [6]:

$$I(a, p) = \sum_f^{N_f} \mathbf{s}_{a,a}(f) e^{2j \frac{2\pi f}{c} d_{a,p}} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{s}_{a,a}(f)$ is the complex reflection coefficient in the frequency domain recorded by antenna a , defined as a vector $1 \times N_f$, where N_f is the number of frequency points. c is the speed of light, $d_{a,p}$ is the electrical distance between each antenna a and a given point in space p (either 1D for a signal or 2D for an image). For image reconstruction, $d_{a,p} = \sqrt{\epsilon_{med}} d_{med} + \sqrt{\epsilon_{body}} d_{body} + d_{off}$, where d_{off} is the offset of each antenna [12], d_{med} is the physical distance traveled in the medium surrounding the body (air or immersion medium) and d_{body} is the physical distance traveled inside the body until reaching point p . ϵ_{med} and ϵ_{body}

Figure 1. Intensity plot of a microwave signal. Red, cyan and green vertical lines corresponds to the maximum of the peak, the point where the slope is the highest and the difference between the two, respectively.

are the average relative permittivities of both media. The intensity ($I(p)$) considering all the antennas is the sum of each antenna contribution $I(a, p)$.

$I(a, p)$ can also be written as $I(d)$, where d is the electrical distance $d_{a,p}$. Equation 2 is used to determine, for each antenna position a , a first estimated distance (d_{e1}) to the body by calculating the location of the maximum magnitude of the first reflection peak. This distance will yield in the ultimate calculation of the model surface.

$$d_{e1} = \arg \max_d I(d) \quad (2)$$

However, the bandwidth of the antenna (which impacts image resolution) and other reflections of the surroundings can increase the width of the first reflection peak and hinder the shape estimation. A second estimation (d_{e2}) may be performed (Equation 3). In case the Half-Width Half-Maximum (HWHM) of the first reflection peak is greater than a user-defined threshold (th), the estimated distance corresponds to the mean between d_{e1} and the distance at which the slope of the peak is greatest (Figure 1).

$$d_{e2} = \begin{cases} \frac{d_{e1} - \arg \max_d \frac{dI}{dd}}{2} & \text{if HWHM} \geq th, \\ d_{e1} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

d_{e1} and d_{e2} correspond to the electrical distance, so the physical distance should be determined dividing it by $\sqrt{\epsilon_{med}}$. Considering each antenna a and the calculated distance, an estimated point of the shape (P_a) can be obtained in the direction of the body. For a circular configuration, the point P_a can be obtained in the radial direction. An optimal threshold (th) can be found for each scenario by considering a known model and minimising the estimation error (e_a), i.e., the difference between the estimated points (P_a) and the retrieved points from the known shape of the model (R_a). For the presented results in this paper, a threshold $th = 8$ mm was empirically determined.

A spline approximation can be used to fit P_a points and create a mask of the body shape. This mask can then be used to determine d_{med} in all directions in the antennas plane for image reconstruction.

Figure 2. 2D slice of (a) a sphere, (b) the irregular-shaped base of the prism, and (c) a breast models.

2.2 Models and data acquisition

Three models (Figure 2) were used to test the proposed methodology in a simulation environment: 1) a sphere of 50-mm radius, 2) a prism with a base of irregular shape, and 3) a Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)-based breast model (ID: 062204) [13]. Each model was surrounded by air ($\epsilon_{med} = 1$) and the relative permittivity and dissipation factor of the model mimicking the body was $\epsilon_{body} = 4.2$ and $\tan(\delta) = 0.01$, respectively. For 1) and 3), a 5-mm radius metallic spherical target was placed inside each model. For experimental validation, the prism with an irregular base and a 4) conical container, filled with Triton X-100, were used in multiple measurements. Triton X-100 is known to mimic the properties of ϵ_{body} as defined above [14].

The considered MMWI prototype is composed of 10 planar monopole antennas [15] operating from 2 to 4 GHz in air, in a monostatic configuration, placed in a circular configuration with radius R . The simulations were performed using CST®Studio Suite 2025. The experimental microwave signals were generated and recorded by a 2-port E5063A ENA Vector Network Analyser (Keysight®). A 11713D Attenuator/Switch Driver (Keysight®) controls a U7110B Multiport Electromechanical Switch (Keysight®) and selects the active antenna from the 10 available ports at any given time. The acquisition is performed automatically using a script developed with MATLAB®2020a and SCPI commands.

3 Results and discussion

Figure 3 shows box-plots of the distribution of the estimation errors e_a for all antenna positions. As expected, the variation of estimation errors per antenna is lower for more regular shapes (e.g. a sphere). The results also show the first estimated distance d_{e1} provides more accurate results for simulated cases. Errors vary from -5.7 mm to 11.2 mm, with a median of 0.4 mm for regular shapes, and vary from -18.7 to 14.8, with a median of -1.0 mm for the irregular shape of the prism. The results also vary with the antenna configuration radius R . The experimental results show the second estimated distance d_{e2} can provide better results for more irregular shapes, decreasing the median error from 11.5 to -2.0 mm.

Figure 4 shows the reconstructed images using the true and estimated shapes of the model and the differential images between the two. Due to space constraints, only the imaging results obtained for models 1) and 3) in simulation are

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. Box-plots of the distribution of the estimation errors for (a) simulated and (b) experimental results. d_{e1} and d_{e2} correspond to the two estimated distances and R corresponds to the radius of the circular antenna configuration.

shown. A spline approximation was used to estimate the shape of the models. Even though the estimation is not entirely accurate, the differential images show there are no significant changes in the reconstructed images and the estimation is satisfactory.

Figure 5 shows the reconstructed images from the experimental signals with the prism and the conical container. The results show the shape estimation is a good approximation of the true shape of the model. We can also observe that, for most estimated points P_a , an offset could be applied to improve the estimation. This offset can be determined for each scenario depending on the antenna configuration. Table 1 shows the impact of applying an offset to all estimated distances d_{e1} on the total estimation absolute errors (i.e. the sum of estimated absolute errors e_a) for four cases. The offset has a limited impact on simulation results, while for the experimental cases it may have a significant impact.

The results show the proposed methodology provides

Table 1. Total estimation absolute errors and impact of applying an offset to each estimated distance d_{e1} .

	Simulation R=75mm		Experimental R=75mm	
	Prism	Breast	Prism	Cone
Initial total error (mm)	63.5	37.0	79.0	46.0
Offset (mm)	-1	-1	-5	-5
Final total error (mm)	62.0 (-2%)	37.0 (0%)	69.0 (-13%)	18.0 (-61%)

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Figure 4. Reconstructed images of simulated signals of (a,c,e) 2D slice of a sphere and (b,d,f) a 2D slice of a breast model, using an circular antenna configuration with $R = 75$ mm. d_{e1} was used for final distance estimation. First row shows the imaging results using the true shape, second row shows the imaging results using the estimated shape and the third row shows the difference between the two. Black dots correspond to the known reference points R_a , red dots correspond to the estimated points P_a , and white dots correspond to the antenna locations.

promising results. Parameters such as the threshold th for the estimation of d_{e2} and the offset applied to the final estimated distance should be optimised for each scenario, i.e. antenna design and antenna configuration. The usage of more antenna positions is expected to increase the accuracy of the method.

4 Conclusions

A method for estimating body shape using microwave signals was proposed, avoiding additional hardware or measuring procedures. The results show the method accuracy is impacted by the irregularity and data source (simulation or experimental). Nonetheless, the results are satisfactory and do not have a significant impact on imaging results.

Future work includes validating this methodology with known and variable anatomically-realistic shapes in experimental settings, and parameter optimisation.

Figure 5. Reconstructed images of experimental signals of (a) a 2D slice of a prism with a base of irregular shape and (b) a 2D slice of a conical container, using an circular antenna configuration with $R = 75$ mm. d_{e2} was used for final distance estimation. Black dots correspond to the known reference points R_a , red dots correspond to the estimated points P_a , and white dots correspond to the antenna locations.

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